

educational level at enrollment was grouped into low, medium, or high, based on the International Standard Classification of Education. We computed age- and sex-adjusted prevalence ratios (PRs) using Poisson regression.

Results: The study included 10,020 persons (42% women) with a median age of 61 years and median diabetes duration 1.2 years. In total, 31% had a low, 50% had a medium, and 19% had a high educational level. Compared to persons with a high educational level, persons with a low educational level were more likely to be obese (58% vs. 49%, PR 1.20 [95% CI 1.14–1.28]), current smokers (22% vs. 15%, PR 1.53 [95% CI 1.32–1.76]), or only physically inactive (21% vs. 15%, PR 1.36 [95% CI 1.20–1.55]). Median HbA1c (48 mmol/mol) and LDL cholesterol (2.1 mmol/L vs. 2.2 mmol/L) were similar across the educational subgroups, whereas persons with a low educational level had more pre-existing cardiovascular disease (CVD) (23% vs. 17%, PR 1.30 [95% CI 1.16–1.46]). Among persons with established CVD, those with a low educational level had similar or greater use of prophylactic pharmacological treatment than those with a high educational level: statins (90% vs. 88%, PR 1.03 [95% CI 0.98–1.07]), ACE inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers (75% vs. 76%, PR 1.00 [95% CI 0.93–1.08]), SGLT2-i (6.5% vs. 5.9%, PR 1.06 [95% CI 0.63–1.78]), and GLP1-RA (9.2% vs. 6.5%, PR 1.30 [95% CI 0.81–2.06]).

Conclusion: Compared to a high educational level, a low educational level was associated with a less healthy lifestyle, obesity, and more CVD in early T2D, but use of prophylactic pharmacological treatment was similar in the two groups.

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Insulin therapy de-intensification with iGlarLixi (IDEAL) randomised controlled trial: CGM-related outcomes

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Background and aims: The IDEAL RCT examined the efficacy and safety of multiple daily injections (MDI) regimen de-intensification into once-daily administered iGlarLixi in people with type 2 diabetes (PwT2D) and showed that it provides comparable glycaemic control with the benefits of reduction of body weight, total daily insulin dose and number of insulin injections and improvement in patients' satisfaction with diabetes treatment. Here we report continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) outcomes from the trial.

Materials and methods: IDEAL was a 5-centre, open-label, parallel-group, phase 4 RCT with a 24-week active treatment period. Participants were randomised in a 1:1 fashion into iGlarLixi or continuation with MDI and were applied professional CGM (Freestyle Libre Pro IQ) 2 weeks before the onset (BL) and for the last 2 weeks of the treatment period (W24). Participants in whom ≥ 72 hours of CGM data were available were included in the analysis.

Results: Altogether 73/91 (80.2%) of IDEAL participants (35/45 participants from the iGlarLixi group and 38/44 participants from the MDI group) had CGM data available and could be included in the analysis. Median (IQR) time in range (TIR, 3.9–10.0 mmol/L) increased in the iGlarLixi group (70 [57–88] at BL vs 80 [61–92] % at W24, $p = 0.039$), but remained unchanged in the MDI group (78 [67–89] vs 82 [64–89] %, $p = 0.728$). In the iGlarLixi group reductions in time above range (TAR, >10.0 mmol/L) (26 [11–44] vs 13 [6–35] %, $p = 0.04$), time in level 2 hyperglycaemia (>13.9 mmol/L) (2 [1–9] vs 1 [0–4] %, $p = 0.019$), mean sensor glucose (8.6 [7.4–10.1] vs 7.7 [6.9–9.2] mmol/L, $p = 0.012$) and glycaemia risk index (GRI) (26 [10–46] vs 19 [8–35], $p = 0.036$) were detected. Median (IQR) time below range (TBR, <3.9 mmol/L) remained unchanged in iGlarLixi group (0 [0–1] vs 1 [0–2] %, $p = 0.337$) and MDI group (0.5 [0–2] vs 1 [0–3.75] %, $p = 0.147$). Statistically significant differences between the changes (BL – W24) in the following CGM metrics (iGlarLixi vs MDI) were observed: coefficient of variation (%CV) (-0.8 [–3.4–0.75] vs 1.4 [–1.2–3.3], $p = 0.016$) and GRI (-3.2 [–22.4–2.4] vs 1.6 [–6.25–10.6], $p = 0.045$).

Conclusion: Insulin therapy de-intensification from MDI into iGlarLixi in PwT2D led to significant improvements in several CGM outcomes vs baseline (TIR, TAR, level 2 hyperglycaemia, mean sensor glucose and GRI) and vs continuation with MDI (glycaemic variability and GRI) without concomitant increase of time spent in hypoglycaemia.

Clinical Trial Registration Number: ClinicalTrials.gov, identifier NCT04945070

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Efficacy and safety of insulin glargine 300 U/mL in insulin-naïve people with type 2 diabetes with/without prior use of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist therapy

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Background and aims: Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1 RAs) lower HbA1c and have a low risk of hypoglycaemia in people with type 2 diabetes (T2D). However, treatment advancement is required if glycaemic targets are not achieved. Insulin glargine 300 U/mL (Gla-300), a second-generation basal-insulin analogue, has a well-established efficacy and safety profile. We assessed the outcomes of initiating Gla-300 in insulin-naïve people with T2D with or without prior GLP-1 RA therapy.

Materials and methods: This analysis pooled Gla-300 efficacy and safety data from 9 interventional and observational studies (BRIGHT, EDITION 3, TAKE CONTROL, REACH, REALI [pooled data from 4 European studies], ACHIEVE CONTROL). People with prior GLP-1